

RADIO FREQUENCY IDENTIFICATION (RFID) - BASED MEDICAL EQUIPMENT MONITORING SYSTEM WITH SHORT MESSAGE SERVICES (SMS) NOTIFICATIONS FOR ONE OF THE HOSPITALS IN THE CITY OF SAN PABLO, LAGUNA

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ABSTRACT

The Radio Frequency Identification (RFID)-Based Medical Equipment Monitoring System with Short Message Service (SMS) Notifications for San Pablo City General Hospital focuses on monitoring the availability of equipment. If it is not available, the status of the equipment is “out,” which means that it was borrowed. The borrower’s and equipment information will be displayed immediately when the ID tag is read. The system consists of four (4) menus such as 1) forms for adding, saving, editing, and updating; 2) equipment monitoring using RFID; 3) a report generator to display information and printouts of reports; and finally, 4) SMS notifications. The objectives of the study are 1) to design a system that can determine the availability and status of the medical equipment; 2) to create a system that will automate the monitoring of medical; 3) to integrate a system Short Message Service (SMS) to the system that remind the hospital’s personnel regarding the scheduled maintenance; 4) to generate reports using crystal report generation technology; and 5) to perform the testing and evaluation using the ISO 9126-1 software quality model. The study used descriptive research, which involves the description, recording, analysis, and interpretation of the present nature, composition, or processes of phenomena, and a modified waterfall model, which has the following phases: requirements analysis, system design, implementation, testing, and maintenance. The evaluation results, in terms of the functionality of the RFID tags and RFID reader,

indicate that 100% of the RFID tags were detected by the reader, which means that the RFID tags and RFID reader were functioning accurately with an average response time of 0.60 seconds. The GSM module indicates that all mobile providers are detected, representing 100% coverage. The response time of the GSM module depends on the area where the mobile provider has a strong signal. The system was found to be functional, reliable, and compatible with a screen resolution of 1366 x 768. The overall mean rating of the responses of the IT experts was 4.64, which means that the system is “completely acceptable”. The Hospital Administrator and staff gave a mean rating of 4.74 with verbal interpretation of “completely acceptable,” and the Supply Officer and staff rated the system 4.95 with a verbal interpretation of “completely acceptable”.

Keywords: *RFID, SMS Notifications, Medical Equipment, Database, Monitoring*

INTRODUCTION

The medical equipment monitoring system is essential for every healthcare facility. Thus, quality monitoring of the equipment ensures that the services are provided safely and effectively. The monitoring system is the regular checking and updating of the current status of health care facilities. It may be used to support equipment needs assessments within the healthcare facility to record the purchase, retirement, and condemnation of equipment. There are modern technologies of monitoring management implemented in some hospitals, but others prefer to use a paper-based or computer-based system approach for checking equipment, which is time-consuming for health personnel. When the volume of patients increased, they needed to eliminate wasted time and get on with the effective workflow. When hospital staff are under pressure, they don't have time to monitor the equipment and sometimes forget the schedule of calibration, which may be risky to their patients. The supply officer of the hospital also experienced tedious work in monitoring, which sometimes resulted in unnecessary errors in recording and retrieving equipment information. This current system was found to have a lot of weaknesses, such as the misuse of the equipment log records, losses of equipment, no in-out transaction record, and misplacement of equipment.

In order to successfully support the hospital personnel in monitoring the medical equipment, a Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) based monitoring system is necessary. An automated monitoring system has features such as storing equipment and employees' data that provide an efficient computer-based system that will easily update, retrieve, and maintain records. A system that gathers information, manages data, and monitors equipment and shared information accurately. Effective monitoring of any type of equipment requires knowing its status, the supplier from whom it was purchased, its fault history, and more. Tapping of RFID tags to quickly look up equipment, which provides reporting of its availability. Reminding personnel about the calibration of equipment using Short Message Services (SMS) will help them maintain the equipment, resulting in high-quality services for patients.

Research Objectives

The SPCGH medical equipment monitoring system includes the installation of RFID readers, linking RFID tags to the database, monitoring the equipment's availability, and notifying personnel of the equipment's maintenance schedule.

General Objective:

The general objective of the study is to develop a Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) - based monitoring system of medical equipment with Short Message Services (SMS) notifications for San Pablo City General Hospital (SPCGH)

Specific Objectives:

1. To design a system that can determine the availability and status of the medical equipment attached with a passive RFID tag that displays the equipment and borrower's information once the RFID reader reads the tag;
2. To create a system that will automate the monitoring of the equipment that records its information, location, and fault history using Microsoft Visual Studio 2008 (VB.NET) and MS Access 2010 for the database.
3. To integrate a system Short Message Service (SMS) into the system that reminds the hospital's personnel three (3) days before the scheduled maintenance, and the assigned personnel will contact the supplier for calibration.
4. To generate reports such as the master list of employees and medical equipment, accountable personnel for the equipment, the maintenance/calibration schedule, borrowers' report, and monitoring report using Crystal Report generation technology ;
5. To perform the testing and evaluation using the ISO 9126-1 model software quality model to identify the quality characteristics, namely: 1) functionality, 2) reliability, 3) usability, 4) efficiency, 5) maintainability, and 6) portability of the system.

Scope and Delimitations

The study covers the development of an RFID-based monitoring system of medical equipment for San Pablo City General Hospital with Short Message Services (SMS) notifications. The RFID reader was used to read the RFID tags, which are located in the lobby of the hospital, for operational testing. The researcher provides only five (5) passive tags attached to the equipment to link the system and RFID readers. The system used MS Access 2010 for the database, which will save the data of the equipment and serial numbers of the tags. The software provides a user account for authorized personnel to access the database, which will let them view the status of the equipment and a maintenance schedule that will remind the assigned staff using SMS.

The system provides an option for generating reports as follows: master list of employees; master list of equipment by category, location, and classification; hospital personnel who are accountable for the equipment; borrowers' report; and monitoring

reports. The system is compatible with any operating system, such as Windows XP, Vista, Windows 7, and Windows 10, provided that serial port drivers are properly installed. Microsoft Visual Studio 2008 (VB.NET) was used in creating the monitoring system.

The system is not Wi-Fi-based but only uses a Global System for Mobile (GSM) module for communication in texting the hospital personnel. The system does not include the maintenance of the equipment since the supplier will do that part. The encoding of all data of the equipment is not covered or done by the researcher because the information about the equipment is confidential. The RFID tags used cannot determine the location of the medical equipment.

Conceptual Framework

The focus of this project is to effectively monitor the medical equipment and notify the personnel of the scheduled maintenance or calibration.

The “input” section contained the knowledge requirements needed in the development of the project. Knowledge requirements include the skills in programming such as Visual Studio 2008 or VB.NET, MS Access 2010, and Structured Query Language (SQL).

The second section contains the “process” which the researcher utilized to attain the objectives of the project, which includes the designing and interfacing of the RFID reader and GSM module, the development of software that consists of an algorithm, pseudocode, flow charting, coding, debugging, and simulation. After the development of the project, testing and evaluation will be done by the IT experts, supply officers, and administration officers in terms of functionality, reliability, and accuracy.

The last section contains the “output,” which is the RFID-based monitoring system with Short Message Services (SMS) notifications for San Pablo City General Hospital. When the RFID tag was tapped into the RFID reader, the system displayed information about the equipment and its status. The system can also provide the following reports: monitoring report or master list of equipment, monitoring report, borrowed equipment outside the hospital, fault report, and maintenance schedule. The system also has the feature of SMS notifications to respective personnel regarding the calibration schedule and faults that have occurred.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Project

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the project or the input-output process approach used in the completion of the system. Input includes the knowledge requirements, hardware, and software requirements. Furthermore, Input consists of the RFID and GSM module designing and interfacing, as well as the software development, testing, and evaluation. Thus, output is the RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) - Based Medical Equipment Monitoring System with Short Message Services (SMS) Notifications.

METHODOLOGY

This section discusses the methods and steps undertaken to develop the project. These steps served as a guide for the researcher in the smooth implementation of the project.

Project Design

The main objective of the study is to develop an RFID-based monitoring system of medical equipment for San Pablo City General Hospital with Short Message Services (SMS) notifications. Rouse (2012) stated that SMS is similar to paging. However, SMS messages do not require the mobile phone to be active and within range, and will be held for several days until the phone is active and within range. Radio frequency identification is a technology that uses electronic tags placed on objects, people, or animals to relay identifying information to an electronic reader by means of radio waves: a toll road equipped with an RFID payment system (Random House, Inc., 2016). RFID readers will

be used to monitor the availability of the medical equipment that will be placed inside the office of the Administrator of the hospital, and one at the lobby. The RFID reader will read the passive RFID tag to display the information about the equipment and to determine the availability of the equipment. When the availability is “out,” then it will display who borrowed the equipment. The serial number of the tag will match the information from the main database. All equipment will have passive RFID tags, which also create an automated monitoring of the equipment. After the designs are made, all materials and equipment will be identified, and the estimated cost will be calculated according to the needs of the hospital. The system for software will also be planned to have automated monitoring. After the hardware and software are ready, testing will be conducted to test their functionality and reliability.

Project Development

The study used Descriptive research and a modified waterfall. Descriptive research involves the description, recording, analysis, and interpretation of the present nature, composition, or processes of phenomena. The focus is on prevailing conditions (Lavina, 2016). Steve McConnell was the first one to describe the Modified waterfall model back in 1996. The modified waterfall model uses the same phases as the pure waterfall model (Rayo, 2015). In response to the perceived problems with the pure waterfall model, the modified waterfall model has been introduced. This enables the phases to overlap when needed. The modified waterfall can also be split into subprojects at an appropriate phase, such as after the hardware design and software design. In response to the perceived problems with the pure waterfall model, many modified waterfall models have been introduced. The phases are as follows: Requirements Definition, System Design, Hardware Design, Software Design, Hardware Requirements, Software Requirements, Block Diagram, Flow Chart, Schematic Diagram, Algorithm, Assemble/Wiring, Hardware Testing, Coding, Software Testing, Hardware and Software Integration, Implementation and Testing.

Hardware requirements:

1) Laptop or Personal Computer

- Processor - INTEL CORE i3 4170 (3.7GHZ, 3MB CACHE, LGA1150) or higher
- Casing - FORTRESS CASING WITH 700WATTS POWER SUPPLY
- Motherboard - INTEL LGA1150
- Hard drive - SEAGATE 1 TERABYTE
- Memory - KINGSTON 2GB to 4GB 1600 DDR3
- Graphics card – optional
- Monitor - ACER 166HQL (15.6) LED or any brand
- A4TECH KRS-8520 PS2 / KRS-8372 USB KEYBOARD AND MOUSE
- Printer - EPSON K200 PRINT//COPY/SCAN/NETWORK or any brand
- UPS (Uninterrupted Power Supply)- APC BK650AS or any brand

2) RFID Reader and RFID Tags

General Specifications:

Operating Voltage : 7.5 to 9V DC

On-board IC : MCU ATmega168

Address Bit Amount : 7 bits
Maximum Cards Registered : 100 (from internal memory alone)
Radio Frequency : 125 KHz
RFID Card Type : 64bit
PCB Dimensions : 46mm x 64mm

3) GSM Module:

Features:

- SIMCom SIM900D Module for SMS, Voice, Data and Fax.
- SIMCom SIM900D Module offers Quad-Band range.
- 3.3V TTL level serial port.
- On-board 3.3V LDO regulator
- Built-in SIM Card holder.

Specifications:

GSM/GPRS Module : SIMCom SIM900D
Multi-band Type : Quad-Band
SIM Card Type : Mini-SIM (ISO/IEC 7810-2003, ID-000)
Length : 2.5 cm
Width : 1.5 cm
Thickness : 0.076 cm
Board Length : 8.3 cm
Board Width : 7.3 cm
Antenna Length : 5.5 cm
Operating Voltage : 5V
Operating Current : 1.50 A

Software Requirements:

Operating System : Microsoft Windows 7 or higher (32-bit or 64-bit)
Application Software : Visual Studio 2008 or higher
Database Software : MS Access 2010 or higher
Screen Resolution : 1366 x 768 (recommended)

Testing Procedures

The hardware for the RFID and GSM modules was both tested after they were assembled. Testing of the hardware components was done using the HyperTerminal. To test the functionality of the RFID reader and GSM module, the researcher attached the adapter and selected a serial port on the computer, then clicked the communication from the accessories of the operating system to finally arrive at Hyper Terminal. As the Hyper Terminal is initiated, a window will appear requesting the desired name of the connection created and the communication port that the connection name 'SPCGH' was typed, and the communication port COM was selected, as shown in Figure 16.

The researcher tested the functionality of the GSM module with different mobile providers such as SMART, Talk n Text, Globe, TM, and Sun.

Testing of the RFID Tags and Reader:

1. The researcher used five (5) passive RFID tags that are attached to medical equipment.
2. The researcher scans the ID using an RFID reader that is connected to the computer to determine if the reader will recognize the tags.
3. The testing includes enrollment of the RFID tags or the saving of the serial number to its corresponding medical equipment into the database.
4. The criteria used to properly evaluate the functionality of the module are a) *response time* – a criterion that pertains to the average response time of RFID reader as reflected into the system; b) *accuracy* – a criterion that pertains to the time registered in the system; and c) *reliability* - a criterion that pertains to the correctness of the computed time based on the time when the ID tags are tapped and time when it was reflected into the system

Testing of the GSM Module:

The researcher used Talk N Text and Smart SIM cards to send SMS notifications to a mobile phone with a SIM card such as Smart, Globe, Talk N Text, and TM. To test the GSM module, the response time was used to determine its functionality.

Project Design Evaluation / Validation

Project Design Evaluation

An evaluation instrument was prepared to evaluate the hardware and software components of the system. The system was presented to ten (10) IT experts to determine its functionality and reliability. The researcher also presented it to the hospital administrator and to the supply officer to determine if the requirements were met. Then the researcher demonstrated it to the administrator's staff and supply staff through a demonstration to explain the objectives and how it works. The evaluators clarified the features of the system. After the demonstration, the researcher requested them to write their evaluation using the instrument.

Project Design Validation

The researcher consulted her thesis adviser and some IT experts for the validation of the instrument to test the content and face validity of the evaluation instrument. After validation, the researcher administered it to ten (10) IT experts, five (5) supply officers and staff, and the hospital administrator, together with the staff. The evaluation instrument was given to them on the day of the testing; subsequently, the evaluation instrument was handed to the researcher to take note of the other comments for final development of the system.

Design Instruments and Techniques

The evaluation tool used a 5-point Likert Scale, which can be interpreted using the numerical rating with descriptive equivalent as follows:

Table 1. Five (5) -Point Likert Scale

Numerical value	Descriptive equivalent	Range of values scale
5	Completely Acceptable	4.51 – 5.00
4	Very Acceptable	3.51 – 4.50
3	Moderately Acceptable	2.51 – 3.50
2	Slightly Acceptable	1.51 – 2.50
1	Not at all acceptable	1.50 and below

After gathering data, the researcher used the weighted mean to determine the acceptability of the newly developed system. It was obtained by the following formula (Statistics.com, 2014): $\sum x/n$, where $\sum x$ was the total sum of all the scores computed using the summary of all responses of the evaluators to determine the acceptability of the system. The rating scales of the evaluation instrument in determining the acceptability of the computed mean are shown in Table 1.

In this study, the Evaluation / Validation Criteria ISO/IEC 9126 standard was used to evaluate and validate the project. This standard presents a set of quality attributes for any software, such as functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability. *Functionality* is the capability of the software product to provide functions that meet stated and implied needs when the software is used under specified conditions. *Reliability* is the capability of the software product to maintain a specified level of performance when used under specified conditions. *Usability* is the capability of the software product to adhere to standards, conventions, style guides, or regulations relating to usability. Efficiency is the capability of the software product to provide appropriate performance, relative to the number of resources used, under stated conditions. *Maintainability* is the capability of the software product to be modified. Modifications may include corrections, improvements, or adaptation of the software to changes in the environment, and in requirements and functional specifications. *Portability* is the capability of the software product to be transferred from one environment to another.

RESULTS

This presents the output of the study, the findings obtained from the different testing methods used, and the results of the evaluation.

Project Technical Feasibility

System Technical Description

Figure 2. The Project and its Components

The developed RFID-based medical equipment monitoring system with SMS notifications is a system that can monitor the availability of the equipment. Medical equipment includes devices such as monitoring equipment, life-support equipment, imaging equipment, laboratory equipment, mechanical equipment, transport equipment, as well as any other equipment supporting the care of a patient, whether or not it is in the immediate vicinity of a patient (Sciencedirect.com, 2025). It uses an RFID reader that determines the status of the medical equipment embedded with RFID tags, shown in Figure 2. The RFID reader is connected to a computer by an RS-232 to TTL converter. The RS-232 to TTL converts the digital data from the reader to serial data to the computer, which is the basis of the software for the programming of the system. The programming language used is Visual Studio 2008, and for the database is Microsoft Access 2010. The GSM module is also connected to the computer. Once the basic assembly of the GSM is completed, and continued with the setup. GSM-GPRS supports the TTL level serial connection, and since the fact that communication ports of present-day computers commonly use either serial or USB ports, a TTL level serial to RS-232 adapter/converter is also used. The power supply for this module is 5 volts DC.

The system provides user accounts to the IT personnel, supply officer, and administration officer. Adding, saving, editing, and updating can be done with the systems by retrieving the forms, such as employees' information, position, department, monitoring, equipment information, category, location, maintenance schedule, faults encountered, and supplier. Monitoring the equipment is done using the RFID reader and tags. The borrowers of the said equipment can be monitored, too. Equipment can be readily viewed by its RFID serial number. Reports are generated as follows: master list of employees, master list of equipment according to location, category, and classification. The assigned personnel for the equipment can also be viewed and reported. The maintenance schedule can be printed so that the supplier can be contacted before the day of calibration.

Project Structure / Organization

The current situation in the monitoring of the equipment is to write in the logbook, and the guard will monitor and release the equipment as the borrower presents the approved papers for borrowing. Once RFID tags, which are attached to the equipment, were read by the RFID reader, the information of the equipment and the borrower was displayed. The database of this RFID system was linked to the system.

DISCUSSION

Project Operational Feasibility

System Design

Presented in Figure 3 is the block diagram of the project. The system software is stored in the computer where the RFID reader is attached. The RFID tags were attached to the equipment where its information was stored in the database, and verified the information that is relayed into the system. The system has a schedule of maintenance, and it reminds the assigned personnel three days before the scheduled calibration or maintenance.

Figure 3. Block Diagram of the Project

Figure 4. System Flow Diagram of the System

The system flow diagram of the system is presented in Figure 4. IT personnel will encode the information of the equipment into the system, eliminating the need to record

using a logbook. With the developed system, medical equipment can be easily monitored. The system retains records of usage, maintenance, and the history of equipment. The system will provide an organized record, inventory, and notification of the scheduled maintenance. It can also provide a hard copy of the equipment's master list, scheduled maintenance, and reports such as equipment information with fault history.

Hardware requirements:

1) Laptop or Personal Computer

- Processor - INTEL CORE i3 4170 (3.7GHZ, 3MB CACHE, LGA1150) or higher
- Casing - FORTRESS CASING WITH 700WATTS POWER SUPPLY
- Motherboard - INTEL LGA1150
- Hard drive - SEAGATE 1 TERABYTE
- Memory - KINGSTON 2GB to 4GB 1600 DDR3
- Graphics card – optional
- Monitor - ACER 166HQL (15.6) LED or any brand
- A4TECH KRS-8520 PS2 / KRS-8372 USB KEYBOARD AND MOUSE
- Printer - EPSON K200 PRINT//COPY/SCAN/NETWORK or any brand
- UPS (Uninterrupted Power Supply)- APC BK650AS or any brand

2) RFID Reader and RFID Tags

General Specifications:

Operating Voltage : 7.5 to 9V DC

On-board IC : MCU ATmega168

Address Bit Amount : 7 bits

Maximum Cards Registered: 100 (from internal memory alone)

Radio Frequency : 125 KHz

RFID Card Type : 64bit

PCB Dimensions : 46mm x 64mm

Figure 5 exhibits the stand-alone RFID Card Reader with built-in MCU ATmega168 with 16kB Flash memory that can store up to 100 RFID cards with a 7-bit address for assigning a number to the users. Additional features on board with Easy "Enroll & Delete" switch with commands, "Execute" push button, "Serial Connection" for monitoring, LED indicators, and Output connection for (ON/OFF) other devices (e_Gizmo_Mechatronix_Central, 2014). It also shows the RFID card (125 kHz) that was used in the project for prototyping.

Figure 5. The RFID Reader and Card

Features of the RFID Reader

- A Stand-alone RFID Card Reader
- With a 2-second delay after tapping.
- Can show the actual Serial number indicated on the card.
- Passive-tag RF I.D. card reader can also detect the type.
- Ease of card reading through distant detection.
- Detects and discerns between registered and unregistered cards.
- Internal memory can register up to 100 RF I.D. cards.
- Easy "Enroll & Delete" user with commands.

3) GSM Module:

Features:

- SIMCom SIM900D Module for SMS, Voice, Data, and Fax.
- SIMCom SIM900D Module offers a Quad-Band range.
- 3.3V TTL-level serial port.
- On-board 3.3V LDO regulator
- Built-in SIM Card holder.

Specifications:

GSM/GPRS Module	: SIMCom SIM900D
Multi-band Type	: Quad-Band
SIM Card Type	: Mini-S#IM (ISO/IEC 7810-2003, ID-000)
	Length : 2.5 cm
	Width : 1.5 cm
	Thickness : 0.076 cm
Board Length	: 8.3 cm
Board Width	: 7.3 cm
Antenna Length	: 5.5 cm
Operating Voltage	: 5V
Operating Current	: 1.50 A

Figure 6. The Global Systems for Mobile Communications (GSM) Module

The GSM Module was used to notify the assigned personnel for equipment maintenance or calibration, as presented in Figure 6 (e-Gizmo_Mechatronix_Central, 2010).

Software Requirements:

Operating System : Microsoft Windows 7 or higher (32-bit or 64-bit)
 Application Software : Visual Studio 2008 or higher
 Database Software : MS Access 2010 or higher
 Screen Resolution : 1366 x 768 (recommended)

Windows 7 was designed to work with today's multi-core processors. All 32-bit versions of Windows 7 can support up to 32 processor cores, while 64-bit versions can support up to 256 processor cores.

Visual Studio 2008 had the following system requirements:

Supported Architectures

- x86
- x64 (WOW)

Supported Operating Systems

- Windows XP Service Pack 2 or above

- Windows Server 2003 Service Pack 1 or above
- Windows Server 2003 R2 or above
- Windows Vista
- Windows Server 2008

Hardware Requirements for Visual Studio 2008

- Minimum: 1.6 GHz CPU, 384 MB RAM, 1024x768 display, 5400 RPM hard disk
- Recommended: 2.2 GHz or higher CPU, 1024 MB or more RAM, 1280x1024 display, 7200 RPM or higher hard disk
- On Windows Vista: 2.4 GHz CPU, 768 MB RAM

Table 2 lists the system requirements for Microsoft Access 2010, such as computer and processor, memory, hard disk, display, operating system, and other requirements, such as graphics card, web browser, application software for importing data, and business connectivity services.

Table 2. System Requirements of Microsoft Access 2010

Component	Requirement
Computer and processor	500-megahertz (MHz) processor or higher.
Memory	256 megabytes (MB) of RAM or higher.
Hard disk	2 gigabytes (GB) of available disk space.
Display	1024 × 768 or higher resolution monitor.
Operating system	Supports only the 32-bit edition of Office 2010: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Windows XP with Service Pack 3 (SP3) • Windows Server 2003 Service Pack 2 (SP2), MSXML 6.0 • Windows Server 2003 R2 Supports both 32-bit or 64-bit editions of Office 2010: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Windows Vista with Service Pack 1 (SP1) • Windows 7 • Windows 8 • Windows Server 2008 • Windows Server 2008 Service Pack 2 (SP2) • Windows Server 2008 R2 • Windows Server 2008 R2 Service Pack 1 (SP1) • Windows Server 2012 • Terminal Server

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Windows on Windows (WOW), which allows installation of 32-bit versions of Office 2010 on 64-bit operating systems, excluding Windows Server 2003, 64-bit and Windows XP, 64-bit. <p>Doesn't support any edition of Office 2010:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Windows Server 2003, 64-bit Windows XP, 64-bit
Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of graphics hardware acceleration requires DirectX 9.0c compatible graphics card with drivers dated 11/1/2004 or later. Internet Explorer 6, Internet Explorer 7, or Internet Explorer 8, 32-bit browser only. Internet functionality requires Internet access (fees might apply). Importing data from Excel 2010 or Outlook 2010 requires Excel 2010 or Outlook 2010. Integration with Business Connectivity Services requires Microsoft .NET Framework 3.5. Product functionality and graphics can vary based on your system configuration. Some features can require additional or advanced hardware or server connectivity. <p>See http://www.office.com/products (http://go.microsoft.com/fwlink/p/?LinkId=169378).</p>

System Overview

The inventory system of SPCGH medical equipment includes the installation of RFID readers, linking RFID into the database, monitoring the status of the equipment with the inventory system, and reminding the personnel of the equipment's maintenance schedule.

- Major functions of the system are to monitor the availability of medical equipment, its inventory, easy retrieval of the assigned personnel to the equipment, generate reports, and remind assigned personnel to contact suppliers for calibration or maintenance of the said equipment.
- The architecture of the system is stand-alone with a server located at the administration office;
- The responsible organization is the developer, who is a graduate student at the Technological University of the Philippines, in cooperation with SPCGH;

- RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) - Based Medical Equipment Inventory System with Short Message Services (SMS) Notifications of San Pablo City General Hospital.
- System category:
Major application: stores equipment and employees' data that provides an efficient computer-based system that will easily update, retrieve, and maintain records.
General support system: provide a system that will serve SPCGH Administrators and Supply Officers with accurate and efficient information in matters related to their equipment inventory
- Operational status:
 - The current system is manual and uses MS Excel for its inventory
 - The system is still developing and will be implemented soon
- System is using Visual Studio 2008 for its software development and MS Access 2010 for the databases.

Logging On

To access the system, the user must have registered the Username and Password. Please contact the admin to register your account. Once you have a user account, you can access the system. Type the Username and Password, then click Accept. The message "Successfully Logged" will appear. The system will prompt an invalid username or password if you enter it wrong. Congratulations, you are now ready to use the main system

System Menu

The System menu is the gateway to human resources information, transactions, and settings. It's called a menu because it provides a list of choices, just as a restaurant menu does.

The FORMS menu, as “form” implies, it’s often the place that you’ll go to open things, Information of Employee information and their departments where they belong, faults encountered, inventory of medical equipment, equipment’s location and category, suppliers’ information, and proper exit of the program.

The Equipment Monitoring menu is the menu that you’ll click to monitor the equipment using the RFID, with the following tabs: enrolment, return, and master list of borrowers. It will display what is the status of the equipment, such as whether it is “in” or “out”. If the status is “in”, there is no borrower, but if it is “out”, the borrower’s information will display. In the enrollment tab, the RFID ID tags are enrolled to which equipment is attached; the return tab displays the equipment and borrower’s information, and if the equipment was returned already.

The Report Generator menu, as “report” implies, it’s the menu that you’ll go to generate a hard copy of the master list of employees according to their department, the master list of equipment, the accountable personnel or assigned personnel to take care of and monitor the equipment, the schedule of maintenance, mobile equipment borrowers, and the inventory report.

SMS Notifications

The SMS Notifications menu is used to notify the assigned personnel to contact suppliers regarding the calibration schedule using the GSM module. An SMS notification, also known as Short Message Service notification (Webex.com, 2025), is a concise text message delivered to mobile devices. All types of businesses and public services can use SMS notifications to inform and alert customers. In this project, the system notifies the accountable personnel of the scheduled maintenance, and they will contact the supplier accordingly.

Figure 7. GSM Module Sending Message to SMART and Talk N Text

The text messages sent by the GSM module to the mobile phone of the assigned personnel with the SIM card SMART and Talk 'N Text.

Using the System

The *Faults Encountered Form* is the screen area for the list of faults and also for adding and changing the information in this form. The data in this form will be used for monitoring the equipment's history.

The screenshot shows a software window titled "Faults" with a green header bar. The main content area is split into two panes. The left pane, titled "Faults", contains a form with the following fields: "Fault Code" (FAC002), "Date Report" (Thursday, October 13, 2016), "Equipment Code" (4421-221), "Equipment Name" (Sterilizers and Autoclaves), "Remarks" (not heating), "Action Taken" (For Repair), and "Date Serve" (11/2/2016 3:16:30 PM). The right pane, titled "List of Faults", contains a table with the following data:

Fault Code	Equipment Code	Remarks	Action Taken
FAC001	POS001	not working, repaired	For Calibration
FAC002	4421-221	not heating	For Repair
FAC003	4421-221	not heating, serve 10/13/16	For Calibration
FAC004	4421-223	calibrate	For Calibration
FAC005	4421-222	Traces have artifacts	For Repair
FAC006	4421-220	no faults encountered, in goo...	Served

At the bottom of the window, there are four buttons: "New", "Edit", "Delete", and "Close".

The *Equipment Form* is the screen area for the detailed information for each equipment and also for adding and changing the information for this form. The data in this form will be used for the generation of equipment details.

The *Location Form* is the screen area for the location of the equipment and also for adding and changing the information for this form. The data in this form will be used to easily track the location of each equipment.

SPGH

Equipment

Equipment Information

Equipment Code: EC000-003
 Category Name: Surgical Instruments
 Equipment Name: Haemostatic Forceps
 Property Tag: 09084
 Description: Stainless
 Serial No.: 56402
 Supplier: unilab
 Location: surgery room
 Assigned Personnel: Asala, Rachel Celine Panaligan

Quantity: 1 Price: 345 Amount: 2070
 Date Purchased: Sunday, 29 January 2017
 Status: For Repair Type: Fixed
 Maintenance Schedule: Saturday, 25 February 2017
 Availability: 1

List of Equipment

Equipment Code	Equipment Name	Assigned Personnel	Property Tag	Location Code
Default				
4421-225	Ultrasound	Nddy, Serfilan Nicolas	092084	surgery room
EC001	Sphygmomanometer	Nddy, Serfilan Nicolas	E16-00019	lobby
POS001	X Ray Film	Nddy, Serfilan Nicolas	092084	lobby
EC000-001	Oxygen Concentrator	Asala, Rachel Celine P.	882	lobby
EC000-003	Haemostatic Forceps	Asala, Rachel Celine P.	09084	surgery room
EC000-002	Electrotherapy device	Agnes, Abigail F.	882	surgery room
4421-221	Sterilizers and Autoclaves	Costales, Soila Masong	00882	housekeeping
4421-222	Ultrasound	Costales, Soila Masong	00882	surgery room
4421-223	Anaesthesia Machine	Costales, Soila Masong	00882	ICU room
EC000-006	Walker	Costales, Ryan Mason	0005953554	admission
EC000-005	Autoclaves	Costales, Ryan Mason	125	housekeeping
EC000-004	Walker	Quizon, Sherwin E.	778	lobby

New Update Delete Cancel

SAN PABLO CITY GENERAL HOSPITAL

Location Code: LOC003

Location: ICU room

List

Location	
lobby	
xray room	
ICU room	
pediatric room	
nurse area	
delivery room	
emergency room	
housekeeping	
maternity ward	
nursery	
operating room	
pharmacy	
surgery room	
wards	

New Edit Delete Close

The *Position Form* is the screen area for the position of the employee in the hospital and also serves to add and change the information for this form.

The screenshot shows a web application window titled "SAN PABLO CITY GENERAL HOSPITAL" with a "Position" header. The "Employee Information" section on the left includes fields for Position Code (P0006), Position (IT Specialist), Department (Information Technology), Salary Grade (30), and Basic Salary (20000). The "List of Information" section on the right is a table with columns for Position Code, Position, and Department.

Position Code	Position	Department
P0000	Other	
P0001	Administrator	
P0002	Chief of Hospital	
P0004	Clerk	
P0005	Radiologist	
P0006	Pediatrician	
P0008	Doctor	
P0009	Nurse	
P0010	Nursing Assistant	
P0011	Human Resource	
P0012	Purchase Officer	
P0013	Cook	
P0014	Nutritionist	
P0015	Desktop Support	
P0016	IT Specialist	

The *Department Form* is the screen area for the employee information and also serves to add and change the information in this form.

The screenshot shows a web application window titled "SAN PABLO CITY GENERAL HOSPITAL" with a "Department" header. It features a Department Code field (D08) and a Department dropdown menu (Information Technology). Below these is a "List" section containing a table of department categories.

Location
Radiology
Patients Account Mgt.
Administration
Out Patient Department
Nursing Department
Budget
Food and Nutrition
Information Technology
ICU
Supply

The *Category Form* is the screen area for the equipment's category information and also serves for adding and changing the information for this form.

SAN PABLO CITY GENERAL HOSPITAL

Forms **Equipment Monitoring** Report Generator SMS Notifications

Category

Category Information

Category Code: CAT001

Category Name
X-Ray Film processor tabletop

Technical Specification
Processing machine for X-ray films from 13x18 cm. 18x24 cm.24x30

List of Information

Category Code	Category Name	Technical Specification
CAT001	X-Ray Film processor L...	Processing machine for X-ray films from 13x18 cm. 18x24 cm.24x30
CAT002	X-ray Film Viewer	X-ray Film Illuminator (Viewer) , 2 Field , Wall-Mount
CAT003	Diagnostic equipment	Thermometer, Sphygmomanometer, Stethoscope
CAT004	Therapeutic equipment	electrotherapy devices, ultrasound, laser therapy and magneto therapy ...
CAT005	Surgical Instruments	Cutting, Grasping or holding, Haemostatic forceps, Retractor
CAT006	Durable medical equa...	Wheel chair, commodes and raised toilet seat, walker and power open...
CAT007	Biomedical equipment	oxygen concentrator, ventilator testing and anaesthesia gas delivery de...
CAT008	Sterilizers	Autoclaves and sterilizers

New Delete Update Cancel

SAN PABLO CITY GENERAL HOSPITAL

Supplier

Supplier Information

Supplier Code: Sup001

Supplier: Plastech

Supplier Abbreviation: PT

Contact Person: Dato Cruz

Address: 234 Bty. Del Remedio, Alabang

Email Address: therera@yahoo.com

Tel No: 048-456690

Mobile No: 0908874887

Fax No: 0244607

List of Information

Supplier Code	Supplier Name	Address	Contact Person	Mobile Number
Sup001	Plastech	234 Bty. Del Remedio, Alabang	Dato Cruz	0908874887
Sup002	unlab	san jose	Juan dela cruz	098887666

New Delete Edit Close

The *Supplier Form* is the screen area for the Suppliers' information that is needed by the assigned personnel to be contacted three (3) days before the scheduled calibration or maintenance. It also serves to add and change the information for this form.

The *Profiling Form* is the screen area for the employee information and also serves for adding and changing the information for this form.

The screenshot shows a software window titled "Employee Information" with a green header. The "Employee No." field contains "E16-00024". The form is divided into several sections:

- Employee Information:** Includes fields for Last Name (Costales), First Name (Solita), Middle Name (Masongsong), Suffix, Date of Birth (13/02/2017), Place of Birth (Bukidnon), Gender (Female), Civil Status (Married), Citizenship (Filipino), Height (5'1"), Weight (47), Blood Type (A), Date Hired (13/02/2017), Date Out (13/02/2017), Employee Status (Probationary), Department (Radiology), Position (Others), Religion (Iglesia Ni Cristo), Contact Person (Reynaldo L. Costales), Contact No. (09081874831), and Address (Brgy. San Jose SPC).
- Family Background:** Includes Spouse (Reynaldo L. Costales), Occupation (unemployed), Business Address, Telephone No., Father (David Masongsong, Sr.), and Mother (Euteria BElen).
- Educational Background:** A table listing schools and graduation dates:

SCHOOL	DATE GRADUATED
*Elementary: Hulo Elem School	1972-78
*Secondary: Mandaluyong High School	1978-82
*Tertiary/Vocational: Rizal Technological University	2008-08

 Highest Educational Attainment: Doctoral with units.

At the bottom, there are buttons for "New", "Update", "Delete", and "Cancel". A "Load Picture" button is located below a placeholder image of the employee.

Figure 8. Employee Registration Window

Figure 8 displays the employee registration form, which is the form used in profiling or encoding the information of the employee. The information is also needed for the equipment assigned to them, and who are also responsible for taking care of the equipment. The form is also used to easily access the information of the employees.

Caveats and Exceptions

This screen will appear in saving data. It says that your data has been successfully saved in the database. Click the OK button to close this dialog box.

This screen will appear in updating the data. It tells that your data has been successfully updated in the database. Click the OK button to close this dialog box.

This screen will appear in deleting data. It tells that your data has been successfully deleted from the database. Click the OK button to close this dialog box.

Report Capabilities

The system has a report available for printing. It was pre-designed during the programming creation.

Master List of Employees

Emp No	Name
Department: Administration	
E16-00023	Agnes, Abegail F
Department: Information Technology	
E16-00026	Costales, Rywin Masongsong
Department: Others in Radiology	
E16-00020	Asaula, Rachel Celine Panaligan
E16-00024	Costales, Solita Masongsong
Department: Out Patient Department	
E16-00018	Quizon, Sherwin B
E16-00017	Try, lang po

Master List of Equipment

Equipment Code	Category Code	Equipment	Supplier Code	Location Code	Employee No.
4421-220	CAT003	Electronic Diagnostic ...	Sup002	LOC007	E16-00024
4421-221	CAT008	Sterilizers and Autocla...	Sup001	LOC008	E16-00024
4421-222	CAT004	Ultrasound	Sup001	LOC013	E16-00024
4421-223	CAT004	Anaesthesia Machine	Sup002	LOC003	E16-00024
4421-225	CAT003	Ultrasound	Sup002	LOC013	E16-00019
EC000-001	CAT007	Oxygen Concentrator	Sup001	LOC001	E16-00020
EC000-002	CAT004	Electrotherapy device	Sup001	LOC013	E16-00023
EC000-003	CAT005	Haemostatic Forceps	Sup002	LOC013	E16-00020
EC000-004	CAT006	Walker	Sup002	LOC001	E16-00018
EC000-005	CAT008	Autoclaves	Sup003	LOC008	E16-00026
EC001	CAT003	Sphygmomanometer	Sup002	LOC001	E16-00019
POS001	CAT001	X Ray Film	Sup001	LOC001	E16-00019

SAN PABLO CITY GENERAL HOSPITAL
Banagale Subdivision, San Jose, San Pablo City

ACCOUNTABLE PERSONNEL

12/02/2017
3:11:50PM

Employee No.: **E16-00018** Department Name.: **Out Patient Department**
Employee Name.: **Quizon, Sherwin B**

<u>EqptCode</u>	<u>Equipment</u>	<u>PropertyTag</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Location</u>
EC000-004	Walker	778	for large	lobby

Employee No.: **E16-00019** Department Name.: **Radiology**
Employee Name.: **Niddy, Santillan Nicolas**

<u>EqptCode</u>	<u>Equipment</u>	<u>PropertyTag</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Location</u>
4421-225	Ultrasound	092084	white	surgery room
EC001	Sphygmomanometer	E16-00019	gray	lobby
POS001	X Ray Film	092084	Table top	lobby

Employee No.: **E16-00020** Department Name.: **Others in Radiology**
Employee Name.: **Asaula, Rachel Celine Panaligan**

<u>EqptCode</u>	<u>Equipment</u>	<u>PropertyTag</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Location</u>
EC000-001	Oxygen Concentrator	882	black	lobby
EC000-003	Haemostatic Forceps	09084	Stainless	surgery room

Employee No.: **E16-00023** Department Name.: **Administration**
Employee Name.: **Agnes, Abegail F**

<u>EqptCode</u>	<u>Equipment</u>	<u>PropertyTag</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Location</u>
EC000-002	Electrotherapy device	882	satinless	surgery room

Employee No.: **E16-00024** Department Name.: **Others in Radiology**
Employee Name.: **Costales, Solita Masongsong**

<u>EqptCode</u>	<u>Equipment</u>	<u>PropertyTag</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Location</u>
4421-220	Electronic Diagnostic Equipment	00882	New	emergency room
4421-221	Sterilizers and Autoclaves	00882	stainless	housekeeping
4421-222	Ultrasound	00882	New	surgery room
4421-223	Anaesthesia :Machine	00882	with ventilator	ICU room

Schedule of Maintenance

Equipment Code	Equipment Name	Property Tag	Description	Supplier	Location Code	Employee No.	Maintenance Schedule	Contact
4421-220	Electronic Diagnostic E	00882	New	unilab	emergency r	E16-00024	28/02/2017	
4421-225	Ultrasound	092084	white	unilab	surgery room	E16-00019	24/02/2017	
EC000-001	Oxygen Concentrator	882	black	Plastech	lobby	E16-00020	02/02/2017	
EC000-002	Electrotherapy device	882	satinless	Plastech	surgery room	E16-00023	02/02/2017	
EC000-004	Walker	778	for large	unilab	lobby	E16-00018	04/02/2017	
EC000-005	Autoclaves	125	Stainless	EliteTech	housekeeping	E16-00026	27/02/2017	

Borrowers' Report

This report generates a schedule of maintenance by month or by date selected by the user.

SAN PABLO CITY GENERAL HOSPITAL

Banagale Subdivision, San Jose, San Pablo City

04/03/2017

EQUIPMENT BORROWERS

<u>EqptCode</u>	<u>EmpNo</u>	<u>LastName</u>	<u>FirstName</u>	<u>DateDue</u>	<u>DateBorrowed</u>	<u>DateReturned</u>
EC000-001	E16-00020	Rodilla	Michelle	01/03/2017 12:00:00A	01/03/2017 12:00:00A	--
4421-221	E16-00026	De Vera	John	01/03/2017 12:00:00A	01/03/2017 12:00:00A	01/03/2017

Inventory Report

SAN PABLO CITY GENERAL HOSPITAL

Search by: Therapeutic equipment Total No. of Equipment:

Print List by:

List of Equipment

Equipment Code	Category	Equipment Name	Property Tag	Location Code	Assigned Personnel	Price	Date Purchased	Status	Type
Default									
4421-222	CAT004	Ultrasound	00882	LOC013	E16-00024	234	02/07/2016	For Repair	Fixed
4421-223	CAT004	Anaesthesia Machine	00882	LOC003	E16-00024	25	23/01/2015	For Calibration	Fixed
EC000-002	CAT004	Electrotherapy device	882	LOC013	E16-00023	1200	29/01/2017	In Range	Fixed

SAN PABLO CITY GENERAL HOSPITAL

Search by: Total No. of Equipment:

Print List by:

List of Equipment

Equipment Code	Category	Equipment Name	Property Tag	Location Code	Assigned Personnel	Price	Date Purchased	Status	Type
Default									
4421-220	CAT003	Electronic Diagnostic E...	00882	LOC007	E16-00024	324	01/08/2016	Good	Mobile
4421-221	CAT008	Sterilizers and Autoclaves	00882	LOC008	E16-00024	465	02/07/2015	For Repair	Mobile
4421-222	CAT004	Ultrasound	00882	LOC013	E16-00024	234	02/07/2016	For Repair	Fixed
4421-223	CAT004	Anaesthesia Machine	00882	LOC003	E16-00024	25	23/01/2015	For Calibration	Fixed
4421-225	CAT003	Ultrasound	092084	LOC013	E16-00019	14000	02/11/2016	Working Fine	Mobile
EC000-001	CAT007	Oxygen Concentrator	882	LOC001	E16-00020	890	29/01/2017	In Range	Mobile
EC000-002	CAT004	Electrotherapy device	882	LOC013	E16-00023	1200	29/01/2017	In Range	Fixed
EC000-003	CAT005	Haemostatic Forceps	09084	LOC013	E16-00020	345	29/01/2017	In Range	Fixed
EC001	CAT003	Sphygmomanometer	E16-00019	LOC001	E16-00019	123	07/11/2016	For Repair	Mobile
POS001	CAT001	X Ray Film	092084	LOC001	E16-00019	9,096	30/08/2016	For Disposal	Fixed
EC000-004	CAT006	Walker	778	LOC001	E16-00018	567	05/12/2016	In Range	Mobile
EC000-005	CAT008	Autoclaves	125	LOC008	E16-00026	567	12/02/2017	In Range	Fixed

Report Procedures

The screen shown above, along with its procedures, can be followed to generate the necessary reports.

Project Evaluation

Testing Results

This section shows the results of the testing based on the functionality and reliability of the project. The tables below provide different testing conditions and the interpretation of the data.

Table 3. Functionality of the RFID Tags and RFID Reader

Equipment	Tag1	Tag2	Tag3	Tag4	Tag5
1	√	√	√	√	√
2	√	√	√	√	√
3	√	√	√	√	√
4	√	√	√	√	√
5	√	√	√	√	√

Table 3 presents the results of the evaluation in terms of the functionality of the RFID tags and the RFID reader. The table shows that all or 100% of the tags are detected by the reader. It means that the RFID tags and the RFID reader are functioning accurately.

Table 4 shows that all or 100% of the mobile providers are detected by the GSM module. It means that the GSM Module was functioning accurately.

Table 4. Functionality of GSM Module

Mobile Provider	User1	User 2	User 3
Smart	√	√	√
Talk n Text	√	√	√
Sun	√	√	√
Globe	√	√	√
TM	√	√	√

Table 5. RFID Response Time Test

RFID Tag	RFID Reader (input)	Actual Output	System Response in seconds	Average Response Time
Tag #1	1:16:02 PM	1:16:03 PM	1 second	0.60 seconds
Tag #2	1:16:04 PM	1:16:04 PM	0 second	
Tag #3	1:16:06 PM	1:16:07PM	1 second	
Tag #4	1:16:08 PM	1:16:09 PM	1 second	
Tag #5	1:16:10 PM	1:16:10 PM	0 second	

The response time test of the RFID tags when tapped into the RFID reader is depicted in Table 5. The researcher enrolled five (5) passive tags, which are attached to the equipment that is used for the monitoring of the borrowing and returning of equipment. The average response time when reflected into the system is .60 seconds.

Table 6. RFID Accuracy Test

RFID Tag	RFID Reader (input)	Actual Output	System Response in seconds	Remarks
Tag #1	1:16:12 PM	1:16:12 PM	0 second	Accurate
Tag #2	1:16:14 PM	1:16:14 PM	0 second	Accurate
Tag #3	1:16:16 PM	1:16:16 PM	0 second	Accurate
Tag #4	1:16:18 PM	1:16:18 PM	0 second	Accurate
Tag #5	1:16:20 PM	1:16:20 PM	0 second	Accurate

Table 6 demonstrated that five (5) RFID tags have accurate readings since the time reflected on the system is the same as the time the RFID tag was tapped on the reader. This means that the tags were accurately detected.

Table 7. GSM Response Time Test

Mobile SIM	SIM of GSM Module			Mean
	Smart	Talk n Text	TM	
Smart	1 sec	1 sec	2 secs	1.33 secs
Talk n Text	1 sec	3 secs	1 sec	1.66 secs
Sun	3 secs	2 secs	3 secs	2.67 secs
Globe	2 secs	5 secs	4 secs	3.67 secs
TM	3 secs	2 secs	2 secs	2.33 secs

Table 7 proved the response time test of the GSM Module reflected on the cellphones of the users. The response time of the GSM module depends on the area where the mobile provider has a strong signal. The table shows that Smart mobile had the strongest signal when the GSM was tested, with a mean of 1.33 seconds, as reflected in the cellphones of the users. Globe mobile provider has the lowest signal in the area when the GSM module was tested, with a mean of 2.33 seconds.

Evaluation Results

To further examine the acceptability of the system, the system was evaluated by ten (10) IT experts, five (5) supply officers, and five (5) administration officers. The evaluators provided some in-depth analysis and feedback on how the system can be improved.

Table 8. Evaluation Results of IT Experts

INDICATORS	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
A. Functionality	4.80	Completely Acceptable
1. Ease of operation	4.80	Completely Acceptable
2. Provision for comfort and convenience	4.60	Completely Acceptable
3. User-friendliness	5.00	Completely Acceptable
B. Usability	4.65	Completely Acceptable
1. The system is significant to the user	4.70	Completely Acceptable
2. Easy to understand and use	4.60	Completely Acceptable
C. Reliability	4.47	Very Acceptable
1. Conformance to desired result	4.80	Completely Acceptable
2. Data recovery when the system is down	4.20	Very Acceptable
3. Ability to recover from system failure	4.40	Very Acceptable
D. Efficiency	4.77	Completely Acceptable
1. Level of performance of the system	4.80	Completely Acceptable
2. Prevents modification of data	4.70	Completely Acceptable
3. Presents accurate information	4.80	Completely Acceptable
E. Maintainability	4.60	Completely Acceptable
1. Ease of maintenance	4.50	Completely Acceptable
2. Provision for diagnostic tools and procedures	4.60	Completely Acceptable
3. Provision for enhancement and Modifications	4.70	Completely Acceptable
F. Portability	4.57	Completely Acceptable
1. Adaptability	4.50	Completely Acceptable
2. Install ability	4.50	Completely Acceptable
3. Replaceability	4.70	Completely Acceptable
Mean	4.64	Completely Acceptable

Table 8 reflected the evaluation results of the ten (10) IT experts. The evaluators gave a mean rating of 4.8 on the *functionality* of the system in terms of ease of operation, provision for comfort and convenience, and user-friendliness with verbal interpretation of “completely acceptable”. In terms of the system’s *usability* with the following criteria: significance to the user and easy to understand and use, the evaluators gave a mean rating of 4.65 with a verbal interpretation of “completely acceptable”. The *reliability* of the system got a mean rating of 4.47 with a verbal interpretation of “very acceptable”. The findings conform to the desired result, no failures found, and the system can perform accurately, but it needs data recovery when the system is down. The table also depicts that the system is “completely acceptable” in terms of *efficiency*, with a mean rating of 4.77. The system can perform according to specifications, provide security as required, and meet the user’s requirements completely. The system also got a mean of 4.6 in terms of *maintainability*, which indicates that the ease of maintenance can be achieved,

provides diagnostic tools and procedures, and the provisions for enhancements and modifications. In terms of *portability*, the evaluators gave a mean rating of 4.57, which means that the system is “completely acceptable”. The mean rating of 4.64 confirms that the system is “completely acceptable”.

Table 9. Evaluation Results of the Supply Officer and Staff

INDICATORS	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
A. Functionality	5.00	Completely Acceptable
1. Ease of operation		
2. Provision for comfort and convenience		
3. User-friendliness		
B. Usability	4.70	Completely Acceptable
1. The system is significant to the user		
2. Easy to understand and use		
C. Reliability	5.00	Completely Acceptable
1. Conformance to desired result		
2. Data recovery when the system is down		
3. Ability to recover from system failure		
D. Efficiency	5.00	Completely Acceptable
1. Level of performance of the system		
2. Prevents modification of data		
3. Presents accurate information		
E. Maintainability	5.00	Completely Acceptable
1. Ease of maintenance		
2. Provision for diagnostic tools and procedure		
3. Provision for enhancement and modifications		
F. Portability	4.93	Completely Acceptable
1. Adaptability		
2. Install ability		
3. Replaceability		
Mean	4.95	Completely Acceptable

It also shows the interpretation of the evaluation of the IT expert with a mean of 4.64, which means that the system is “completely acceptable”. One of the IT experts commented that the modules are complete and working, and the integration of mobile or SMS notifications made the system very good. Another expert commented that the

system is easy to use but needs a backup and restore facility for data recovery in case of failure or error. The experts observed that the information system has met the requirements, but should provide more data recovery when the system is down and enhance the procedure and diagnostic tools.

The evaluation results of the supply officer and staff is presented in Table 9. They rated the system with a mean rating of 4.95 with a verbal interpretation of “completely acceptable”. They commented that the operation is easy to understand, the application is very useful and accurate but suggested connecting it to other institutions of the local government.

Table 10. Evaluation Results of the Administration Officer and Staff

INDICATORS	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
A. Functionality	4.80	Completely Acceptable
1. Ease of operation		
2. Provision for comfort and convenience		
3. User-friendliness		
B. Usability	4.80	Completely Acceptable
1. The system is significant to the user		
2. Easy to understand and use		
C. Reliability	4.80	Completely Acceptable
1. Conformance to desired result		
2. Data recovery when the system is down		
3. Ability to recover from system failure		
D. Efficiency	4.67	Completely Acceptable
1. Level of performance of the system		
2. Prevents modification of data		
3. Presents accurate information		
E. Maintainability	4.60	Completely Acceptable
1. Ease of maintenance		
2. Provision for diagnostic tools and procedures		
3. Provision for enhancement and modifications		
F. Portability	4.80	Completely Acceptable
1. Adaptability		
2. Install ability		
3. Replaceability		
Mean	4.74	Completely Acceptable

Table 10 depicts the evaluation results of the administration officer and staff. The table depicts that the administration department gave a rating of 4.74, which means that the system is completely acceptable.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The system was successfully developed according to its objectives in determining the availability of the medical equipment using the attached passive RFID tag.
2. The software application was successfully created to automate the monitoring of the equipment, which records its information, status, and fault history using Microsoft Visual Studio 2008 (VB.NET) and MS Access 2010 for the database.
3. The integration of Short Message Service (SMS) into the system that reminds the hospital's personnel three (3) days before the scheduled maintenance and the assigned personnel who will contact the supplier for calibration was successfully done.
4. The system can generate reports by displaying the queries and printing the following: master list of employees and medical equipment, accountable personnel, the maintenance schedule, borrowers' report, and monitoring report using Crystal Report generation technology.
5. The system was tested and evaluated using the ISO 9126-1 model software quality model to identify the quality characteristics, namely: 1) functionality, 2) reliability, 3) usability, 4) efficiency, 5) maintainability, and 6) portability of the system.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the following are hereby recommended:

1. The system may be implemented by the hospital, focusing on its services and having a good management system for its medical equipment.
2. To use an active RFID reader for long-range monitoring of equipment that can track where the equipment is located.
3. To enhance the notifications by integrating a database of messages that can receive and read messages from the supplier. Automatic messaging when the system detects that the calibration schedule is approaching.
4. To view the system using screen resolution 1366 x 768, which is the most widely supported resolution by monitors as of today.
5. To include diagnostic tools and recovery of the data when the system fails.
6. To modify the system by using Wi-Fi and networking technology to communicate with other computers and link the system to other institutions connected to the hospital.
7. To conduct further research that continuously updates and develops a system to cope with the current technological trends

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The universities required the researcher to submit an *Ethical Conduct of Research* before conducting the conduct of survey. The guidelines are:

- Determine the protocol that ensures that the participants' information and data are anonymized; methods applied involve minimal risks; data collected is not personal or sensitive and would not place participants at risk if inadvertently disclosed.
- The researcher must report any unanticipated problems and/or adverse events that involve risk to (University's name-URC (University Research Center) within one week of the investigator becoming aware of this unanticipated problem or adverse event. They may contact the U-URC by email (not to mention) for questions or more information.
- Ethical Principles Required
 - Honesty: Honestly report data, results, methods, and procedures. Do not fabricate, falsify, or misrepresent data.
 - Objectivity: Strive to avoid bias in experimental design, data analysis, data interpretation, peer review, expert testimony, and other aspects of research.
 - Informed Consent/Confidentiality: Protect confidential communications, respondents' records, trade, and personnel secrets.
 - Competence: Maintain and improve your own professional competence and expertise through lifelong education and learning.

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